

The linear accelerator

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Particles with the charge Q and the mass m are accelerated with voltages (see figure).

From tube to tube we have the same acceleration voltages U . First we calculate the classical case - the velocity of the charged particle is very small compared to the light velocity c . At the n -th tube we get:

$$\frac{mv_n^2}{2} = E_{kin} = n \cdot Q \cdot U$$

The kinetic energy E_{kin} is equated with the product of n and the electric work. It follows:

$$v_n = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot n \cdot Q \cdot U}{m}}$$

If we know the frequency f in the linear accelerator, we can calculate the length s_n of the n -th tube:

$$s_n = v_n \cdot \frac{T}{2} = \frac{v_n}{2f} \quad \text{with} \quad T = \frac{1}{f}$$

f = frequency

T = oscillation period

With that we obtain:

$$s_n = \frac{1}{2f} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2nQU}{m}}$$

Now we deal with the relativistic case. The velocity of the particle must not be small compared to the light velocity c . In this case we have to equate the kinetic energy with the electric work, too.

$$mc^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_n^2}{c^2}}} - 1 \right) = E_{kin} = n \cdot Q \cdot U$$

We transform to v_n , and we obtain with equation (2) see Schröder [1]:

$$v_n = c \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{E_{kin} + mc^2} \right)^2}$$

Insertion of the electric work:

$$v_n = c \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{n \cdot Q \cdot U + mc^2} \right)^2}$$

With $s_n = v_n \cdot \frac{T}{2}$ and $T = \frac{1}{f}$ we follow at last:

$$s_n = \frac{c}{2f} \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{n \cdot Q \cdot U + mc^2} \right)^2}$$

Then the relativistic case is dealt with, too.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Geschwindigkeit und Temperatur" 2009
- [2] Harald Schröder "Particular problems of special relativity theory" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002